

THE IMPORTANCE OF GRAMMAR IN WRITING IELTS AND WAYS TO IMPROVE IT

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Abstract: This article is about the importance of grammar in writing, and the article gives understanding of it. Grammar plays a key role not only in writing, but also in speaking. It describes how to achieve accuracy and fluency through the correct use of grammatical structures in IELTS writing. Even when describing charts in IELTS task1, it is difficult to describe if your grammar is not good. There are some tips and books for developing grammar in this article .

Key words: accuracy, credibility, readability, clarity, language proficiency, communication, cohesion, coherence, cohesive devices, improving grammar.

INTRODUCTION

English plays a crucial role in the development of education systems around the world because of the usage of English language. Nowadays we can find out majority data and researches in English. Grammar is an important aspect of learning English language. A number of grammatical errors and difficulties can occur among students when learning English because of the poor knowledge of students with grammar in their daily life. There are many books are written by native speakers which is about English grammar. For example: Grammar for IELTS by Liz, Practical English usage by Michael Swan, Simon's Grammar and etc. Grammatical errors are huge problem because great and creative ideas can be missed due to misunderstandings that grammatical errors can cause. To avoid this we have to learn grammar structures thoroughly. Grammar plays a crucial role in creative writing, credibility, readability, communication and clarity. In order to mastering grammar will allow to you to make your work as a writer more clear and readable.

Main body

Grammar is one of the most essential aspects of IELTS not only in writing but also in four aspects (listening, reading, writing, speaking) . Wrong usage of grammar may effects our band score. In writing we should use various grammatical structures to express our opinions and arguments. Without learning grammar we can not achieve

this points. When we use grammar correctly, we can communicate clearly and create an impression someone's mind. To do this, we must follow on some parameters:

1. *Cohesion and Coherence* - coherence and cohesion are crucial for helping readability and communication. Coherence is about full idea and cohesion the unity of systematic components. If we use cohesive devices: logical bridges (repetition), verbal bridges (synonyms), linking words and clear back referencing through our sentences. Our writing not only becomes more easily to read the text, but also to understand it's meaning easier when sentences connected with cohesive devices.

2. *Demonstrating Language Proficiency* – language proficiency relates to a person's production and development of a particular language. Proficiency test scores reflect a person's ability to communicate in the language being tested. We demonstrate our level by using grammatical structures that examiners will evaluate our language proficiency.

3. *Clarity and Precision* – we must focus on clarity and precision in writing. By accuracy the ideas we express which must reach the reader clearly and fluently and create an image in his/her mind. Precision is about specific and accurate which involves selecting the perfect words to express our thoughts removing any vagueness and avoiding generalities.

4. *Conveying Meaning Accurately* – IELTS writing tasks require candidates to express their points of view, analyze data and present arguments logically. Grammar serves as a tool to express your thoughts correctly. Whether you describe trends in a graph, showing pros and cons or expressing your opinion in an essay. Grammatical accuracy ensures that you clearly convey your intended meaning. Misplaced modifiers, subject-verb agreement errors or incorrect sentence structures can derail your message, leading to a low score. It's really important to have an outline of things that you want to say. Keep it simple sometimes you want to make your text look amazing and use all the advanced words but this is a great tip if you are writing an academic essay.

Three tips on how to improve your English grammar:

1. *Keep a grammar journal*: write down new grammar rules and examples as you learn them. Review your notes regularly to reinforce your understanding and track your progress.

2. *Play grammar games*: engage with educational games and puzzles focused on grammar. These can make learning fun and help reinforce concepts through repetition. Grammar games help students or children not only gain knowledge but be able to apply and use of language will increase

3. *Seek feedback*: share your writing with teachers or peers who can provide constructive feedback understanding, their corrections will help you identify patterns in your mistakes and improve over time. Feedbacks can motivate us We can feel self – confidence day by day.

Conclusion

The main purpose of creating a text is to deliver a thought and if you overcomplicated. It might be too hard to deliver a thought. By correcting our grammar mistakes, we acquire clarity. It is our weakness if we do not understand some parts even when we are reading a topic or theory. For anyone who wants to score high in IELTS writing, realize the role of grammar when we face difficulties. To avoid this situation, we need to master grammar well. When the foundation is strong, everything is easy.

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